

Small mammal (rodents and lagomorphs) European biogeography from the Late Oligocene to the mid Pliocene

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ABSTRACT

Aim To analyse the fossil species assemblages of rodents and lagomorphs from the European Neogene in order to assess what factors control small mammal biogeography at a deep-time evolutionary time-scale.

Location Western Europe: 626 fossil-bearing localities located within 31 regions and distributed among 18 successive biochronological units ranging from *c.* 27 Ma (million years ago; Late Oligocene) to *c.* 3 Ma (mid Pliocene).

Methods Taxonomically homogenized pooled regional assemblages are compared using the Raup and Crick index of faunal similarity; then, the inferred similarity matrices are visualized as neighbour-joining trees and by projecting the statistically significant interregional similarities and dissimilarities onto palaeogeographical maps. The inferred biogeographical patterns are analysed and discussed in the light of known palaeogeographical and palaeoclimatic events.

Results Successive time intervals with distinct biogeographical contexts are identified. Prior to *c.* 18 Ma (Late Oligocene and Early Miocene), a relative faunal homogeneity (high interregional connectivity) is observed all over Europe, a time when major geographical barriers and a weak climatic gradient are known. Then, from the beginning of the Middle Miocene onwards, the biogeography is marked by a significant decrease in interregional faunal affinities which matches a drastic global climatic degradation and leads, in the Late Miocene (*c.* 11 Ma), to a marked latitudinal pattern of small mammal distribution. In spite of a short rehomogenization around the Miocene/Pliocene boundary (6–4 Ma), the biogeography of small mammals in the mid Pliocene (*c.* 3 Ma) finally closely reflects the extant situation.

Main conclusions The resulting biogeographical evolutionary scheme indicates that the extant endemic situation has deep historical roots corresponding to global tectonic and climatic events acting as primary drivers of long-term changes. The correlation of biogeographical events with climatic changes emphasizes the prevalent role of the climate over geography in generating heterogeneous biogeographical patterns at the continental scale.

Keywords

Biogeography, controlling factors, macroecology, Neogene, similarity analysis, small mammals, species distribution, western Europe.

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INTRODUCTION

When compared with modern Asian and North American mammal faunas, extant European mammal faunas typically show low levels of diversity and high levels of endemism. This situation is usually explained by the geographical configuration of the European continent, with a relative reduction of land surface area

from Asia towards western Europe, leading to a westward decrease in biodiversity, and by the existence of refuge areas during the glaciation phases of the Plio-Pleistocene glacial cycles (e.g. Baquero & Tellería, 2001). Here we address the question of the origin of this strongly heterogeneous biogeographical configuration, looking at the evolutionary history of European small mammals with regard to long-term geographical and climatic

changes. We selected two orders of herbivorous small mammals, rodents and lagomorphs, for three complementary reasons based on present day (reasons 1 and 3) and fossil (reasons 1 and 2) evidence: (1) their well-known systematic and evolutionary history, (2) their high relative abundance in vertebrate fossil localities, and (3) their relatively high sensitivity to the various biotic or abiotic environmental parameters (e.g. temperature and precipitation, vegetation density, etc.) that control population dynamics and spatial distribution of species at a local–regional scale (Erb *et al.*, 2001).

The interregional and deep-time historical approach we develop has two aims: (1) to describe the evolution of the biogeographical patterns that took place during the last 25 million years (that is to say, and as far as we know, during times of origination and diversification of most of the modern mammal families), and (2) to search for the controlling parameters that drive these observed long-term changes through time (Ricklefs, 2004). In such an approach, the levels of biogeographical and time resolution, depending on the quality and quantity of data to hand, are crucial points deeply affecting the ecological and evolutionary meanings and implications of the inferred patterns of change (Wiens, 1989; Allen & Holling, 2002).

Several biogeographical analyses of Tertiary European mammalian faunas have actually already been undertaken. Most of these studies focus on the Neogene (the last 24 million years), when a major deterioration of climatic conditions was experienced, with the replacement of a tropical context by a more temperate one in Europe. This time span is a key period in the evolutionary history of mammals, when ‘archaic’ Palaeogene faunas were progressively replaced by ‘modern’ Neogene faunas having a family composition similar to extant ones (e.g. Fahlbusch, 1989). At an intercontinental scale, different phases of faunal migration and dispersion are known [e.g. the arrival of cricetid rodents from Asia and proboscideans from Africa through the ‘*Gomphotherium* Land Bridge’ linking the European continent to the Anatolian Plate at the end of the Early Miocene (c. 18 Ma); the arrival of murine rodents, or the arrival of gerbilid rodents and camels from Africa at the end of the Late Miocene (c. 6.5 Ma) (Fahlbusch, 1989; Geraads, 1998; Mein, 1999a)]. At an intracontinental scale, faunal reactions to climatic fluctuations have been described (e.g. Agustí, 1989; Fortelius *et al.*, 1996). All of these studies have led to a better knowledge of the evolutionary history of mammals thanks to the identification of broad biogeographical patterns. For instance, during the Neogene, the distribution of some large mammal taxa (e.g. ungulates) appears to be restricted, leading to a differentiation of faunal compositions between western and eastern Europe (Fortelius *et al.*, 1996) and between southern and northern Europe (Costeur *et al.*, 2004). Based on the distribution of rodent taxa, faunal differentiations are illustrated between the eastern and central Iberian Peninsula (Agustí, 1989), and faunal homogeneity is observed in peri-Mediterranean areas during Late Miocene–Early Pliocene times (Geraads, 1998).

Even though the spatial continuity of the European terrestrial fossil record is not complete, because of the unevenness of the geological context, the increased quality and spatio-temporal

density of the Late Oligocene and Neogene (Miocene and Pliocene) mammal fossil record now provides material to perform synthetic biogeographical studies at a closer, regional level of resolution. The analysis of the tempo and mode of biogeographical pattern changing through time at such a regional scale allows characterization of the differential impact of geographical, climatic and historical events on species distributions. Indeed, faunal assemblages identified at such a regional scale can be considered as first-order proxies for metacommunities, i.e. ‘sets of local communities that are linked by dispersal of multiple interacting species’ (Leibold *et al.*, 2004). Variations in species richness at such a regional scale are known to be strongly dependent on historical constraints (e.g. origination, extinction and migration rates; Hillebrand & Blenckner, 2002) and thus on geographical and climatic conditions at the continental level (Arita & Rodríguez, 2004). This makes the regional meta-community level an ecologically meaningful level of functional organization, having its own dynamics and interaction rules partly emerging from local community integration and partly determined by controlling physical and historical parameters at the continental level (Ricklefs, 1987, 2004; Leibold *et al.*, 2004). Hence, we predict that a deep-time historical regional approach considering the whole European continent over c. 24 Myr will help to clarify these patterns and help the understanding of the present-day low diversity and heterogeneous situation in the light of known palaeogeographical and palaeoclimatic events.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Temporal and spatial settings

The data set used in this study includes 626 small mammal fossil localities (a detailed list is available on request from the corresponding author) distributed within 18 successive biochronological units ranging from c. 27 Ma (Late Oligocene; Palaeogene reference levels MP28 to MP30) to 3.2 Ma (mid Pliocene; Neogene biozones MN1 to MN15) (BiochroM’97, 1997; Mein, 1999b). These biochronological units represent time spans of c. 0.7 to 2.5 Myr (median time span c. 1 Myr; Escarguel *et al.*, 1997; Steininger, 1999). They are defined at the European level on the basis of associations of some diagnostic mammal species with large geographical ranges. For each biochronological unit, a reference locality provides the typical association of evolutionary stages (‘morpho-species’, or ‘chrono-species’; see below) observed in phyletic lineages. These associations allow the relative dating of other faunas. Thus, biochronological units are characterized at the continental level by faunal assemblages without marked phases of origination, extinction or migration events, whereas such events are used to define the limits of these biochronological units. Consequently, each regional taxonomical assemblage defined in this study, for each biochronological unit, can reasonably be considered as a stable pool of species regionally coexisting throughout the corresponding time span.

The data set includes localities covering Europe from the western Iberian Peninsula to Greece (including Crete), extending into northern Europe. The Balkans (former Yugoslavia), which

Table 1 List of the 31 analysed regions, including the country, the geological characterization, the estimated surface area and the abbreviations used in Appendix S1. The numbers in the left column refer to Fig. 1

	Country	Region	Geological context	Estim. area (km ²)	Abbreviations
1	Portugal	Tagus Basin	Sedimentary basin	13,000	POR
2	Spain	Granada-Guadix-Baza	Sedimentary basin	44,000	GBG-S
3	Spain	Madrid-Guadalajara	Sedimentary basin	43,000	MAD-S
4	Spain	Duero	Sedimentary basin	62,000	DUE-S
5	Spain	Jucar-Albacete	Sedimentary basin	9500	JUC-S
6	Spain	Alicante-Murcia	Sedimentary basin	8000	ALI-S
7	Spain	Calatayud-Daroca-Teruel	Sedimentary basin	10,000	CDT-S
8	Spain	Castellon-Valencia-Alcoy	Sedimentary basin	8000	CAS-S
9	Spain	Ebro	Sedimentary basin	39,000	EBR-S
10	Spain	Vallés-Penedés and S. Urgell	Sedimentary basin	20,000	VPU-S
11	France	Aquitain basin and Quercy	Sedimentary basin and fissure fillings	70,000	AQU-F
12	France	Languedoc-Roussillon	Sedimentary basin	30,000	LAN-F
13	France	Paris Basin	Sedimentary basin	30,000	PAR-F
14	France	Central Massif	Sedimentary basin	28,000	CMA-F
15	France	Ardèche	Sedimentary basin	12,000	ARD-F
16	France	Provence	Alpine foreland molassic basin	26,000	PRO-F
17	France	Centre-Est	Sedimentary basin and fissure fillings	14,000	CEE-F
18	Switzerland	Swiss. Molasse Basin	Alpine foreland molassic basin	24,000	SWI
19	Germany	RheinHessen	Sedimentary rift basin	40,000	RHE-G
20	Germany	Baden-Württemberg and Bayern	Alpine foreland molassic basin and fissure fillings	60,000	BWB-G
21	Italy	Piedmont	Sedimentary basin	10,500	PIE-I
22	Italy	Toscany	Sedimentary basin	26,000	TOS-I
23	Austria	Styrian & Vienna basins	Sedimentary basins	36,000	AUS
24	Czech rep.	Bohemian Massif	Sedimentary basins	18,000	CZE
25	Slovakia	West Slovakia	Sedimentary basins	6000	SLO
26	Hungary	Pannonian Basin	Sedimentary basin	40,000	HUN
27	Poland	South Poland	Carpathian foreland depression and fissure fillings	61,000	POL
28	Romania	North Dacic Basin	Sedimentary basin	60,000	RUM
29	Bulgaria	South Dacic Basin	Sedimentary basins	60,000	BUL
30	Greece	Macedonia	Sedimentary basin	40,000	MAC-G
31	Greece	Central Greece and islands	Sedimentary basin	150,000	CEN-G

contain too few known localities, were excluded from the analysis. The western part of the former Soviet Union has also not been included because of the paucity of comparative studies with the rest of Europe. Each of the 31 regions considered in this study is defined by a set of localities from a same, ‘homogeneous’ geological unit such as a sedimentary basin or a geological formation (Table 1 & Fig. 1). All but one (‘Greece’, including the central Greek region and islands that are currently notably distant but were markedly closer during the Neogene; Meulenkamp & Sissingh, 2003) represent surface areas ranging from *c.* 6000 km² to *c.* 70,000 km² (geometric mean of *c.* 25,000 km²), making them fully comparable to the present-day mosaics of landscapes which constitute ecological regions. The surface area of each region is estimated as the rectangle encompassing all known fossil localities, based on the minimum and maximum latitude and longitude coordinates recorded in the set of localities.

Data set construction

The systematic compilation of the 626 localities was undertaken following a three-step procedure. First, taxonomy was standardized

at the morphological species and phyletic lineage levels using published systematic revisions (e.g. Rössner & Heissig, 1999). When no taxonomic revisions were available, the original author(s) point of view was followed. Second, all the local faunas from each region and biochronological unit were pooled into taxonomically standardized regional lists of phyletic lineages. Third, all regional lists for a given biochronological unit were brought together, leading to the construction of 18 successive presence/absence matrices (available on request from the corresponding author). In all of these matrices, regions with fewer than four identified families of rodents or lagomorphs show noticeably higher variability in species richness than regions with four or more families, suggesting potential sampling biases. Consequently, they were a priori eliminated from the biogeographical matrices. The number of localities and species for each region and biochronological unit is presented in Table 2.

Analysis at the phyletic lineage level involves evolutionary rather than strictly typological (morphological) considerations about the very nature of the biological entities under study. A phyletic lineage is a hypothesized, genealogically continuous anagenetic line of descent (i.e. a chronological series of interbreeding

Figure 1 Location of the 626 mammal fossil-bearing localities and of the 31 European faunal regions considered in this study (see Table 1 for names of the regions).

individual organisms), genetically and morphologically evolving through time as the result of the dual mechanisms of the accidental origin of genetic variation and the design action of development and natural selective demands (see Gingerich, 1985). Analysis at such an evolutionary level eliminates the spurious, somewhat artificial problem of pseudo-origination and extinction at the species level, a phyletic lineage being defined by one or more successive ‘chrono-species’, i.e. arbitrary morphological evolutionary stages within a continuous anagenetic line of descent. Consequently, when several chrono-species were defined as parts of a phyletic lineage, they were coded as a single entry in the analysed data set.

Processing method

Each biogeographical matrix was separately analysed using the coefficient of taxonomic similarity of Raup and Crick (1979). This probabilistic index is the confidence level associated with a unilateral randomization test, which involves, for each pair of compared regions in a given biogeographical matrix, the following null and alternate hypotheses. (1) H_0 : the species observed in the two regions are distributed between them by random sorting from a common pool of species made up of all the species recorded in the biogeographical matrix. Thus, this hypothesis of the random sprinkling of species that are considered as

independent from one another implies that the observed number of species common to both regions is only due to chance. (2) H_1 : the similarity observed between the two regions is higher than would be expected as a consequence of the random sorting from a common pool of species. Hence, a couple of regions characterized by a very high Raup and Crick index value (say, $RC > 0.95$) show a significant similarity between their studied taxonomic assemblages (they non-randomly share too many taxa in common); conversely, a couple of regions characterized by a very low Raup and Crick index value (say, $RC < 0.05$) show a significant difference between their studied taxonomic assemblages (they non-randomly share too few taxa in common). For each pair of regions, the associated null distribution of the number of shared species was estimated by generating 999 successive random resamplings from the common pool of species without taking into account the observed probabilities of species occurrence.

Once computed, the 18 resulting matrices of similarity (S) were converted into matrices of dissimilarity (D) using the transformation $D = 1 - S$, and then clustered using the neighbour-joining (NJ) method of phenogram reconstruction (Saitou & Nei, 1987; program NEIGHBOR from the PHYLIP v. 3.5 package, Felsenstein, 1993). The NJ algorithm is a widely used distance-based heuristic method of phylogenetic inference (Felsenstein, 2004). From a given observed dissimilarity matrix, it allows the computation of the shortest total length additive tree with the branch lengths estimated by unweighted least squares. As a consequence of the weak metricity of the analysed dissimilarity matrices, most of the inferred NJ trees showed some short branches with negative length (allowed by the NJ algorithm). Such branches were a posteriori eliminated from graphic representations by collapsing their associated nodes — as a negative branch length is obviously biogeographically meaningless, though justifiable from a strict statistical point of view considering the observed distances as random variable estimates (Felsenstein, 2004).

A complementary synthetic parameter is given for each biogeographical matrix: the median value of the Raup and Crick similarity coefficient (SCM) and its associated nonparametric 50% confidence interval (first–third quartile), which can be interpreted as a robust index of faunal homogeneity (inter-regional connectivity, or ‘cosmopolitanism’).

RESULTS

Impact of sampling or analysis parameters on the taxonomic similarity analysis

When studying (palaeo)biogeographical affinities using taxonomic similarities, one must first check that: (1) species richness is not correlated to sampling or analysis parameters, such as the number of localities and surface area of each region or time span represented by each successive biochronological unit, and (2) taxonomic similarity is not correlated to the interregional difference in species richness, number of localities, surface area or time duration of biochronological units.

Table 2 Number of analysed localities and identified species in each region and for each biochronological unit. Regions with fewer than four identified rodent and lagomorph families (shaded cells) were excluded from the analysis. The time divisions refer to the Mammal Palaeogene (MP) biochronological scale for the Late Oligocene (MP28 to MP30, c. 27–23.9 Ma) and to the Mammal Neogene (MN) biochronological scale for the Miocene and Pliocene (MN1 to MN15, c. 23.9–3.2 Ma; see Materials and Methods for details)

		Region																															European Total		
		01 - Tagus Basin	02 - Guadix-Baza + Granada	03 - Madrid-Guadalajara	04 - Duero	05 - Jucar-Albacete	06 - Alicante-Murcia	07 - Calatayud-Daroca-Teruel	08 - Castellon-Valencia-Alcoy	09 - Ebro	10 - Vallés-Penedés + S.Urgell	11 - Aquitain Basin + Quercy	12 - Languedoc-roussillon	13 - Paris Basin	14 - Central Massif	15 - Ardèche	16 - Provence	17 - Centre-East	18 - Swiss Molasse Basin	19 - Rheinhessen	20 - Baden-Württemberg + Bayern	21 - Piedmont	22 - Toseany	23 - Styrian & Vienna basins	24 - Bohemian Massif	25 - West Slovakia	26 - Pannonian Basin	27 - South Poland	28 - North Dasic basin	29 - South Dacic basin	30 - Macedonia	31 - Central Greece + Islands	European Total		
Plio.	Early	MN 15	9	26		5	1	2					5						1						2	1	1	3		2			32		
	MN 14	3	11	12		1	8	8	2	3		11	27		1		3	18	2						22	19	19	18	1	1	5	26	48		
Miocene	Late	MN 13	8	17	3		5	14	2				2					2	1			1	4			1	9				7	23	50		
		MN 12					3	4	9	12		1	2	11		1	2	10					3	18							3	12	15		
		MN 11					2	8	8	11		2	3			2	7	17	3		1		1	3	2	24								25	
		MN 10	2	7				2	12			11	12	3	19			2	4	33					8		1				5	13	36		
		MN 9			3	1	8	6	4	12		9	32	1	7	5			2	17	1	1	3	23		4	16		1	13	1			32	
		MN 7-8	1	6	1	1	8	8	2	5		5	4	5	17			5	13	32	38		3	24		1	2		2	13			1	4	68
	Middle	MN 6	1	11	3			5				2	10	21	27			11	6	1	7	13			4	12								52	
		MN 5	3	12	3	5		9	20		1	6	19	4	17			2	7	44	27	19	33		5	16						3	10	77	
		MN 4			5			11	6	25	26	4	13	33	28	13		2	11			4	8	37	2	19	17		1	9			1	22	92
	Early	MN 3	2	11	1	3		5	18	5		2	7	9	5					4	18	3	25		1	2									42
		MN 2b			2	9		2	14		1	8	2	12	17	9				2	8	2	7	3											17
		MN 2a			2	6					3	17	4	1	14	5	16		1		3	23	1	9		Number of localities								20	
		MN 1			1	6				2		14	2	17	14	2	12			16	2	5	35				Number of species								33
	Oligocene	Late	MP 30		1	3						4	17		3			1	15	10	24	11	22												25
			MP 29		3	10			1	12			1	13		3	15				8	25	14												
MP 28				2	5			1	17	5	7	3	22		2	11				5	20	2	24												20

Because of the high sampling intensity characterizing Spain, France and Germany, and the relatively lower sampling intensity of Eastern Europe, the number and richness of sampled localities vary noticeably between regions. Nevertheless, such variations do not have a preponderant impact on the inter-regional differences in species richness (Fig. 2a): in spite of a significant log–log linear correlation due to a logical asymmetrically bounded relationship, the variation in number of localities in a region explains no more than one-third of the variation in regional species richness. On the other hand, as the regions’ areas represent surfaces ranging from c. 6000 km² to c. 150,000 km² (Table 1), and the successive biochronological units represent time spans ranging from c. 0.7 to 2.5 Myr, such heterogeneities could at least partly control the regional variations in species richness observed

through space and time. Figure 2(b, c) shows that this is actually not the case. Concerning the species–area relationship, the observed independence holds when analysing it at the biochronological unit level (graphs not shown here), with Spearman rank correlation values ranging from –0.31 to 0.69, none of them being significant at the 95% nominal confidence level after a Holm’s correction for multiple tests of the corresponding *P*-values. Concerning the species–duration relationship, this empirical result is supported by independent theoretical considerations about the impact of the duration of the biochronological unit on species richness counting (Escarguel & Bucher, 2004).

Finally, taxonomic similarity values appear to be statistically independent of their corresponding ‘inter-regional species richness standardized differences’

Figure 2 Log–log relations between the regional species richness (SR , dependent variable) and (a) the number of localities ($SR = 9.92 \times NL^{0.372}$; $r^2 = 0.32$, $P < 0.001$; Spearman $\rho = 0.586$, $P < 0.001$), (b) the region's area ($SR = 16.56 \times Area^{-0.013}$; $r^2 = 4 \times 10^{-4}$, $P = 0.85$; Spearman $\rho = 0.037$, $P = 0.65$; area values in km^2 estimated from Fig. 1), and (c) the time duration of each biochronological unit [$SR = 14.43 \times TS^{0.03}$; $r^2 = 5 \times 10^{-4}$, $P = 0.79$; Spearman $\rho = 3.2 \times 10^{-3}$, $P = 0.97$; TS values in million years estimated from Escarguel *et al.*, 1997 (MP) and Steininger, 1999 (MN)] for the 18 successive biogeographical matrices.

$$\delta_{ij}^{SR} = \frac{|SR_i - SR_j|}{\max(SR_i, SR_j)},$$

where SR_i and SR_j are the species richness values of regions i and j , respectively (Fig. 3). In exactly the same way (graphs not shown here), taxonomic similarity is also independent of their corresponding: (1) standardized difference for the number of localities in each region (Spearman $\rho = 9.6 \times 10^{-3}$, $P = 0.82$), (2) standardized difference for the log-area of each region (Spearman $\rho = -0.046$, $P = 0.26$), and (3) time duration of biochronological unit (Spearman $\rho = 0.042$, $P = 0.31$). Finally, the independence observed between taxonomic similarity values and δ_{ij}^{SR} holds when analysing this relationship at the biochronological unit level (graphs not shown here), with Spearman ρ values ranging from -0.35 to 0.64 , none of them being significant at the 95% nominal confidence level after a Holm's correction for multiple tests of the corresponding P -values.

These first results strongly suggest that the observed inter-regional taxonomic similarities, as well as their evolution through time, cannot be considered as the single, direct or indirect by-product of the heterogeneities in species richness, number of localities, area or time interval. They therefore legitimize, all other things being equal, the search for other factors controlling the observed biogeographical patterns.

Evolutionary trends of inferred biogeographical patterns

The similarity analysis of the 18 biogeographical matrices (see Appendix S1 in Supplementary Material) allows the identification of five successive time intervals with distinct biogeographical characteristics (Figs 4–8). The time limits of these intervals correspond to the four major faunal changes (high turnover rates) classically recognized in Europe during the Neogene: two intercontinental migrations of faunas from Asia and Africa at the end of the Early Miocene and at the Middle–Late Miocene boundary; the drying of the Mediterranean Sea at the end of the Late Miocene; and the beginning of glacial cycles at the mid

Figure 3 Relationship between the 'inter-regional species richness standardized difference' (see text for definition) and the Raup and Crick similarity coefficient (Spearman $\rho = -0.054$, $P = 0.15$; based on a Mantel test with 9999 permutations).

Pliocene. This time division has already been proposed by Fahlbusch (1989) to describe a five-step evolutionary history of European mammals from the Late Oligocene to mid Pliocene.

Because eastern European localities are unknown to date for the Late Oligocene and Early Miocene times (first time interval; Table 2), we reanalysed the biogeographical matrices from MN4 to MN15 (*c.* 18–3.2 Ma) without taking them into account in order to control the biogeographical results for a geographical diffusion effect (Fig. 9). The almost perfect congruence of the SCM curves obtained with and without the eastern European localities clearly indicates that the biogeographical trend obtained from the complete data set is not a spurious by-product of the increase in the total geographical area analysed from the MN4 biochronological unit onwards.

Figure 4 Biogeographical trees illustrating the faunal affinity patterns of the first identified time interval. The time divisions refer to the Mammal Palaeogene (MP) biochronological scale for the Late Oligocene (MP28 to MP30, c. 27 Ma to 23.9 Ma) and to the Mammal Neogene (MN) biochronological scale for the Miocene and Pliocene (MN1 to MN15, c. 23.9 Ma to 3.2 Ma; see Materials and Methods for details). The period considered in this figure spans MP28 to MP30 for the Palaeogene and MN1 to MN3 for the Neogene, c. 27 Ma to 18 Ma. Phenograms were constructed using the neighbour-joining method with negative-branch allowed (Saitou & Nei, 1987; program NEIGHBOR from the PHYLIP v. 3.5 package, Felsenstein, 1993). The reference scale (R.S.) allows one to compare the branch lengths of the trees from MP28 to MN15.

First time interval: Late Oligocene to Early Miocene (MP28–MN3, c. 27–18 Ma; Fig. 4)

During the first time interval, the biogeographical context shows a high faunal homogeneity all over Europe (high SCM values, with almost no significantly dissimilar pairs of regions; Table 3, Fig. 9 and Appendix S1). Consequently, no clear biogeographical cluster emerges from the resulting phenograms, which show very simple structures with almost no trifurcating nodes (Fig. 4).

Nevertheless, several points are noteworthy. The south-western French faunas in most cases show high affinities with the Iberian ones, especially with those from the northern part of the peninsula. The other French regions are biogeographically located between the northern and southern European ones. Faunal affinities of the Aquitanian Basin are especially variable through time. During Late Oligocene times, this basin presents greater affinities with the Spanish Basin than with the rest of Europe, as previously described by Comte (2000). During Early Miocene times, no clear biogeographical pattern can be identified, while southern Germany generally shows lower affinities with the rest of Europe.

The general faunal homogeneity in Europe is consistent with what is known from species distributions. Most of the

species are present in all the European regions, evidencing that no important biogeographical barriers act on their distribution. Indeed, Werner (1994) already showed that taxa particularly useful in large-distance chronological correlations, such as *Pseudotheridomys parvulus*, *Myoglis tuyolsi*, *Rhodanomys transiens* and *Eucrietodon gerandianus*, can be found from Germany to the Iberian Peninsula. From the data used in this study, many other lineages also present a large geographical distribution in all the European regions from the Upper Oligocene to the Lower Miocene.

Concerning the eastern part of Europe, too few data allow the affinity pattern to be described. But the discovery of the Anatolian cricetid *Mirabella* in Germany (de Bruijn & Saraç, 1992) leads the authors to suspect that no major biogeographical barrier existed along eastern Europe.

Second time interval: end of the Early Miocene to Middle Miocene (MN4–MN7/8; c. 18–11.1 Ma; Fig. 5)

Numerous significant faunal dissimilarities appear between regions (see Appendix S1), indicating a non-random structuring of faunal assemblages into sets of biogeographically homogeneous regions, as illustrated by the corresponding biogeographical trees (Figure 5). With respect to the previous time interval, a

Figure 5 Biogeographical trees illustrating the faunal affinity patterns of the second identified time interval. The period considered for each tree is indicated by the biochronological unit [Mammal Neogene (MN)], from biozone MN4 to MN7/8, c. 18–11.1 Ma. The inferred biogeographical affinities allow the grouping of regions into clearly individualized biogeographical provinces (dashed boxes). Phenograms were constructed using the neighbour-joining method with negative-branch allowed (Saitou & Nei, 1987; program NEIGHBOR from the PHYLIP v. 3.5 package, Felsenstein, 1993). The reference scale (R.S.) allows one to compare the branch lengths of the trees from MP28 to MN15.

Figure 6 Biogeographical trees illustrating the faunal affinity patterns of the third identified time interval. The period considered for each tree is indicated by the biochronological unit [Mammal Neogene (MN)], from biozone MN9 to MN12, c. 11.1–6.5 Ma. Same legend as Fig. 5.

Figure 7 Biogeographical trees illustrating the faunal affinity patterns of the fourth identified time interval. The period considered for each tree is indicated by the biochronological unit [Mammal Neogene (MN)], biozones MN13 and MN14, c. 6.5–4 Ma. Same legend as Fig. 5.

Figure 8 Biogeographical tree illustrating the faunal affinity patterns of the fifth identified time interval. The period considered for each tree is indicated by the biochronological unit [Mammal Neogene (MN)], biozone MN15, c. 4–3.2 Ma. Same legend as Fig. 5.

clearer biogeographical pattern thus emerges from longer and more complex trees, an evolution summarized by a marked decrease in the SCM (Table 3 & Fig. 9).

Throughout the end of the Early Miocene and the Middle Miocene, the north-east–south-west dissimilarity gradient first observed evolves towards a more north–south one. This faunal differentiation identified at the species level can also be observed at the genus level, with the presence in northern Europe of rodent genera unknown in southern Europe (e.g. Fejfar, 1990). The Iberian Peninsula faunas cluster with the southern French ones and clearly constitute a unique biogeographical entity. At the beginning of the Middle Miocene, the Greek faunas show high dissimilarities with the rest of Europe, but generally seem to cluster with central and eastern European ones.

At the end of the Lower Miocene (MN4), the arrival of Asian and African elements increases the interregional dissimilarities between assemblages and creates a new biogeographical pattern (Fahlbusch, 1989; Agustí, 1999); especially with the distribution of new cricetids as early as MN4 (c. 18–17 Ma): e.g. *Democricetodon hispanicus* is restricted to the Iberian Peninsula whereas *Democricetodon gracilis* is present all over Europe except in Iberia.

Third time interval: Late Miocene (MN9–MN12; c. 11.1–6.5 Ma; Fig. 6)

During the Late Miocene, the biogeographical trees remain long and complex, while the SCM keeps decreasing, evidencing a more and more heterogeneous biogeographical context with strong isolation of some regions (e.g. Austria and Hungary during MN10, c. 9.7–8.7 Ma; Table 3 & Fig. 9). The association of the Iberian Peninsula and southern France observed previously is still individualized. The Greek faunal affinity with eastern Europe disappears (MN10 and MN12, c. 9.7–6.5 Ma) and its affinities with the southern part of Europe increase. The north–south biogeographical gradient is now totally established, the MN12 pattern probably being non-significant due to the extremely low number of compared regions.

This faunal differentiation is clearly obvious with murid rodents, first appearing exclusively in southern Europe (MN9: *Occitanomys hispanicus* and *Progonomys catalai*). Then, from MN10 onwards, they are found everywhere, but stay clearly rare in the northernmost regions (Austria, Germany and Hungary) whereas they are very diversified in southern regions, especially southern France and Iberia (Michaux *et al.* 1997). Such latitudinal structuring of the murid diversity is very likely to be the direct consequence of their high sensitivity to climatic parameters, especially temperature (Aguilar *et al.*, 1999).

Fourth time interval: Miocene–Pliocene boundary (MN13–MN14; c. 6.5–4 Ma; Fig. 7)

A renewed faunal homogeneity occurs in Europe throughout the terminal Miocene and the beginning of the Pliocene (Figs 7 & 9). This short biogeographical event is linked to the Messinian age, when the level of the Mediterranean Sea dropped (Clauzon *et al.*, 1996), creating broad land bridges between southern Europe and northern Africa. During this time interval, the faunal affinities of the Greek region with other southern European ones subsist, and more generally all peri-Mediterranean faunas show a relatively high faunal homogeneity. Such a homogenization makes the Messinian (MN13, c. 6.5–4.9 Ma) biogeographical pattern difficult to decipher, especially because of the low number of known localities in northern regions. Nevertheless, a south-western

Figure 9 (a) Boxplots [median (first–third) quartiles and (min–max) values] of the Raup and Crick taxonomic similarity coefficient. The solid and dashed grey lines correspond to the SCM computed with and without the eastern European regions, respectively (see text for details). The time divisions refer to the Mammal Palaeogene (MP) and to the Mammal Neogene (MN) biochronological scales (see Materials and Methods for details). (b) Global trend (mean and observed range) on deep-sea temperature fluctuations deduced from the worldwide oxygen isotope record. For the considered time span, this $\delta^{18}\text{O}$ record mainly reflects changes in Arctic and Antarctic ice volume (adapted from Zachos *et al.*, 2001, Fig. 2). The roman numerals in the central column refer to the time intervals described and discussed in the text.

biogeographical unit (still including all Iberian faunas) subsists, and the beginning of the Pliocene still documents the north–south faunal gradient.

Fifth time interval: mid Pliocene (MN15; c. 4–3.2 Ma; Fig. 8)

During this last biochronological unit, four sets of regions can be clearly identified on the corresponding biogeographical tree (Fig. 8). The lowest SCM value observed since the Upper Oligocene (illustrating a strong faunal heterogeneity within Europe) emphasizes the strengthening of the faunal differentiation, inducing high dissimilarities for geographically distant regions. At that time, a very high provincialism, quite close to the extant situation, characterizes the European biogeographical pattern.

For instance, Romania stands out as a strongly individualized entity despite its rather close geographical proximity to Hungary. These observations differ markedly from the pattern emerging from the previous biochronological unit. Nevertheless, the absence of truly south–eastern regions does not allow the full recognition of the north–south gradient evidenced in MN14 (c. 4.9–4 Ma).

Based on our data set, very few species present a large geographical distribution for this period, when compared with the previous ones. This observation is also supported by some fossil endemic species. For example, the Romanian and Greek regions present an obvious faunal isolation with typical species: *Pliospalax macovei*, *Pliospalax rumanus*, *Cricetulus simionescui*, *Micromys kozaniensis*, *Romanocastor filipescui*, *Zamolxifiber covurluensis*, *Ochotona ursui* (Macarovici, 1973).

Table 3 Median (SCM), corrected median (cSCM, calculated without eastern regions) and (first–third) quartiles of the Raup and Crick taxonomic similarity coefficient. The time divisions refer to the Mammal Palaeogene (MP) biochronological scale for the Late Oligocene (MP28 to MP30, *c.* 27–23.9 Ma) and to the Mammal Neogene (MN) biochronological scale for the Miocene and Pliocene (MN1 to MN15, *c.* 23.9–3.2 Ma; see Materials and Methods for details)

			SCM	[1 st q.; 3 rd q.]	c SCM	[1 st q.; 3 rd q.]	
Plio.	Early	MN 15 _{3.2 Ma}	0.253	[0.076; 0.687]	0.443	[0.130; 0.918]	
		MN 14 _{4.9 Ma}	0.878	[0.051; 0.998]	0.949	[0.814; 0.998]	
	Late	MN 13	0.639	[0.480; 0.937]	0.833	[0.316; 0.979]	
		MN 12	0.256	[0.080; 0.746]	0.335	[0.018; 0.833]	
		MN 11	0.558	[0.206; 0.805]	0.645	[0.208; 0.738]	
		MN 10	0.370	[0.208; 0.736]	0.718	[0.126; 0.862]	
	MN 9 _{11.1 Ma}	0.529	[0.137; 0.814]	0.447	[0.214; 0.714]		
Miocene	Middle	MN 7–8	0.520	[0.227; 0.868]	0.546	[0.371; 0.890]	
		MN 6	0.833	[0.291; 0.937]	0.821	[0.376; 0.942]	
		MN 5 _{17.0 Ma}	0.642	[0.151; 0.925]	0.601	[0.266; 0.929]	
	Early	MN 4	0.903	[0.472; 0.997]	0.952	[0.903; 0.992]	
		MN 3	0.943	[0.623; 0.991]	0.941	[0.467; 0.991]	
		MN 2b	0.752	[0.598; 0.920]	0.752	[0.598; 0.920]	
		MN 2a	0.895	[0.726; 0.956]	0.895	[0.726; 0.956]	
		MN 1 _{23.9 Ma}	0.927	[0.786; 0.995]	0.927	[0.786; 0.995]	
	Oligocene	Late	MP 30	0.959	[0.908; 0.974]	0.959	[0.908; 0.974]
			MP 29	0.723	[0.292; 0.919]	0.723	[0.292; 0.919]
MP 28 _{27.0 Ma}			0.863	[0.582; 0.929]	0.863	[0.582; 0.929]	

DISCUSSION

Impact of tectonic and geographical controlling parameters

During the last 25 Myr, European geography has changed drastically, leading to the demarcation of the coastline and the elevation of mountain ranges that characterize the extant configuration. In order to get an evaluation of the impact of geography over biogeography, we superimposed the significant similarities and dissimilarities of the Raup and Crick index on palaeogeographical maps for the seven biozones with the most complete fossil record, illustrating the evolution of the biogeographical pattern through different geographical contexts (Fig. 10).

Several tectonic events and geographical changes punctuate the European Late Oligocene and Neogene geological history. Large structures such as mountain chains or sea channels can act as geographical barriers for dispersal and are often cited as possible factors enabling speciation by vicariance, ultimately leading to the evolution of endemic pools of species, and thus to significant regional diversity and biogeographical differences. Through distinct and localized tectonic pulses, the overall European tectonic evolution is driven by the Alpine Cycle, corresponding to the convergence of the European and African-Arabian plates. This large cycle, still active today, has long been shaping the whole of European geography, and not solely that of the close peri-Alpine and Alpine domains. Prior to the period considered here, the Pyrenean Orogenic Phase, related to the Alpine Cycle, led to the formation of the Pyrenean mountain chain in the Late Eocene (major tectonic pulse around 34 Ma) and thus triggered the appearance of a potential geographical barrier between the Iberian Peninsula and the rest of western Europe. Likewise, the European Cainozoic Rift System (Rhine and Rhône grabens)

was largely flooded in its northern part (Rhine graben) during the Late Oligocene to Early Miocene (Meulenkamp & Sissingh, 2003) and could have constituted a geographical barrier. Even though both the Pyrenean mountains and the Rhine graben could have been expected to produce marked faunal dissimilarities between the regions they separate, our results indicate that strong interregional affinities and no significant dissimilarities actually characterized the studied area during Late Oligocene and Early Miocene times. Then at that time, rodent and lagomorph assemblages appear biogeographically homogeneous and relatively unaffected by such geographical barriers.

Later on, the continued anticlockwise rotation of the African Plate led to a junction between the Arabic and Anatolian plates and the Balkans known as the ‘*Gomphotherium* land bridge’ (Rögl, 1999). This new terrestrial domain enabled the arrival in Europe of numerous mammalian species from Asia and Africa (Mein, 2003), and was coeval with the emergence of a marked biogeographical pattern and the individualization of biogeographical provinces during biozone MN4 (*c.* 18–17 Ma; Fig. 5). Unlike for large mammals (Costeur *et al.*, 2004), the onset of this continental corridor, which can be viewed as a potential source of faunal homogenization through a facilitation of migrations, did not generate higher affinities between regional rodent and lagomorph assemblages. Despite the establishment of the ‘*Gomphotherium* land bridge’, small mammal assemblages located in the Anatolian Plate are significantly different from the rest of the European ones. The lack of palaeontological record in the Anatolian Plate before MN4 does not allow the characterization of the faunal affinities of this region before *c.* 18 Ma. Indeed, due to a long period of isolation of Anatolia from Europe by a large sea channel, it seems likely that this region had a particular faunal assemblage, with more affinities with Asian faunas than with European ones.

Figure 10 Significant similar and dissimilar Raup and Crick index values superimposed over palaeogeographical reconstructions of the European continent for the seven most sampled biochronological units. The palaeogeographical maps are taken and modified from Jones (1999), Rögl (1999) and Meulenkamp & Sissingh (2003). The time divisions refer to the Mammal Palaeogene (MP) and to the Mammal Neogene (MN) biochronological scales (see Materials and Methods for details).

Even though several tectonic phases punctuate the Middle and Late Miocene (e.g. the eastern European Styrian and Attic phases, corresponding to the emergence and formation of the Greater Caucasian mountains and affecting all the Alpine foreland basins; Meulenkamp & Sissingh, 2003), the overall biogeographical context still presents a lot of significant affinities on a north-east–south-west transect. The affinities of the regions close to the Alpine foreland basins are not significantly more affected than the others. A significant dissimilarity now appears between the more distant regions; only the closer regions keep a significantly similar faunal composition whereas the more distant north-eastern and south-western regions remain significantly dissimilar through the Late Miocene. The geographical

context alone fails to explain the slight biogeographical change that starts at this period.

The last set of large tectonic pulses that can be considered in the context of this study are: (1) the Rhodanian phase, from the end of the Miocene and during the Pliocene, affecting southern European geography with a marine incursion in the Rhodanian Valley and all the peri-Alpine and peri-Carpathian foreland basins, (2) the connection of some isolated regions such as the Italian Peninsula and southern Iberian basins, and (3) the second phase of rifting of the Rhine graben around 4–3 Ma, leading to the present continental outline (Meulenkamp & Sissingh, 2003). Once again, such events could be expected to lead to specific biogeographical patterns. However, during MN14 (*c.* 4.9–4 Ma) this

new context provides no significant differentiation between eastern and western Europe, a single value being significant between the southern Iberian faunas and the Greek ones. The biogeographical pattern appears to be a general north–south differentiation unaffected by the geographical context. Finally, during MN15 (c. 4–3.2 Ma), only closer regions maintain significant faunal similarities, especially between both sides of the Pyrenean range. The pattern turns out to be very heterogeneous, with a strong north–south differentiation, and still without obvious relation with the geographical context.

In conclusion, both significant similarities and dissimilarities observed between regions indicate that the evolution of the biogeographical pattern never clearly matches the geographical context. Indeed, a relatively homogeneous biogeographical pattern can be observed during the Late Oligocene and Early Miocene, when important geographical barriers (mountain ranges or rift valleys) are known in Europe. Then, small mammal assemblages turn out to be more and more heterogeneously distributed throughout the Miocene and the Pliocene, with almost no overlap of the inferred biogeographical patterns with potential physiological barriers. Obviously, such observations do not mean that the geographical context has absolutely no effect on species distribution and patterns of interregional diversity and faunal similarity, but strongly suggests the presence of other controlling factor(s) in order to explain the inferred biogeographical patterns and their evolution.

Untangling factors that control the interregional biogeographical relationships

At the broad European scale, the evolution of the Raup and Crick index median value (SCM) from the Late Oligocene to the mid Pliocene summarizes the evolution of the global biogeographical context (Table 3 & Fig. 9). It allows the identification of a significant overall decreasing trend in interregional faunal affinities, as estimated by a ‘runs test above and below the mean’ after the removal of MN13 and MN14 values, which are clearly linked to a non-global event (see below; observed number of runs: $N_{\text{obs}} = 4$; expected number of runs for $N_{\text{below}} = 7$ and $N_{\text{above}} = 9$: $N_{\text{exp}} = 8.875$; $P = 0.01$). This overall trend of decreasing SCM through time is punctuated by three major biogeographical events, namely the mid Miocene, the Messinian and the mid Pliocene events.

First, SCM stayed high throughout the Late Oligocene to the Early Miocene, mimicking the rather homogeneous conditions inferred from plants (Bruch *et al.*, 2004), then decreased from the Middle to the Late Miocene. This evolution towards lower interregional faunal connectivity levels can be linked to the global climatic change known as the ‘mid Miocene event’, related to the development of a permanent East Antarctic Ice Sheet (Flower & Kennett, 1994). This major event triggered a worldwide decrease in the deep-sea oxygen isotopic record and is equated to a gradual global cooling from c. 14 Ma onwards (Zachos *et al.*, 2001; Figure 9). This climatic event led to a major environmental change seen in palaeovegetation assemblages, with the worldwide expansion of low-biomass vegetation. Likewise, the emergence of a pattern of latitudinal distribution of the vegetation seems to be the con-

sequence of a strengthening of temperature gradients in the mid latitudes (Wolfe, 1985). It is noteworthy that the latitudinal biogeographical pattern described in this paper fits the latitudinal climatic pattern that takes place during the Middle Miocene.

The second major event is a rehomogenization of the biogeographical context during the latest Miocene and earliest Pliocene. This event, starting in the Messinian, i.e. part of biozone MN13 (c. 6.5–4.9 Ma), was a short (630 kyr; Clauzon *et al.*, 2005) environmental change only affecting the peri-Mediterranean area. During this time interval, the interruptions of the Atlantic–Mediterranean connection, due to sea level fall and tectonic activity in the Betic and Rifian corridors, led to a Mediterranean drawdown (Clauzon *et al.*, 1996; Meulenkamp & Sissingh, 2003). New land connections were then created and faunal exchanges occurred between the European and African continents (van der Made, 1999) even though some authors proposed that the entry of African micro-mammals slightly preceded the very Messinian event (Krijgsman *et al.*, 2000). The arid climate, already present in southern Europe before the crisis, probably favoured the drying of the Mediterranean Sea once Gibraltar closed up, the sea’s hydrological budget being highly negative (Blanc, 2000). After the Messinian event, the environmental context around the Mediterranean Sea still reflects a latitudinal organization of the vegetation, but mosaic regional arrangements as already observed by Suc *et al.* (1995) are superimposed onto this overall pattern and can explain the faunal context for this interval (MN13–14, c. 6.5–4 Ma).

The third major event occurred in the mid Pliocene (between biozones MN14 and MN15, c. 4 Ma), with a drastic decrease in the SCM value evidencing a strong heterogeneity among European faunas. This event was coeval with the interruption of the Early Pliocene climatic optimum as illustrated by the appearance in Europe of the first cricetid rodents with a sigmodont-like tooth pattern. This trend to faunal heterogeneity can thus be directly related to the first evidence of climatic deterioration towards coolness and dryness, indicating the onset of glacial cycles as early as 3.2 Ma.

Among these three major changes, the mid Miocene and the mid Pliocene events were global climatic events that both induced a reinforcement of biogeographical heterogeneity at the broad European scale. In contrast to this, the Messinian event was a more restricted and shorter environmental disturbance, primarily controlled by tectonics, which acted to reorganize the diversity distribution within the peri-Mediterranean domain. Indeed, the isotopically well-established global climatic degradation illustrated by the fall of temperatures throughout the Neogene, closely paralleled the observed overall trend of increase in faunal heterogeneity (Fig. 9).

Based on these observations, it appears that global climatic change is the key to understanding the evolutionary trend of European faunal affinity during Neogene times. Some authors have already described such a relationship between long-term faunal dynamics and global climatic parameters and events (e.g. Legendre, 1987). On the one hand, when a weak climatic gradient applies, such as during the Late Oligocene and Early Miocene, the environmental conditions appear quite homogeneous all over Europe (Bruch *et al.*, 2004), with generally warm and humid,

sub-tropical conditions. In this context of weakly contrasted climate, the interregional biogeographical affinities are high and appear to be almost uninfluenced by geographical factors. On the other hand, when a marked climatic gradient applies, such as during the Late Miocene and Pliocene, faunal affinities present a latitudinal structuring mainly controlled by climatic parameters. During and just after the Messinian (biozones MN13 and MN14, c. 6.5–4 Ma), intra- and intercontinental migrations rehomogenized species distribution in the peri-Mediterranean area (southern Europe), i.e. between regions that belong to the same climatic zone. Hence, this event also illustrates the overall importance of climatic zonation on species distribution.

CONCLUSION

The regional level analysis of Late Oligocene to mid Pliocene European rodent and lagomorph species distributions presented in this paper illustrates the evolutionary trend that led the Palaeogene biogeographical context to become heterogeneous throughout Neogene times. Such an evolution can be divided into three successive biogeographical phases: (1) before c. 18 Ma, strong interregional taxonomic affinities go with a homogeneous climatic context in Europe, (2) from c. 18–11 Ma, regional faunal assemblages become increasingly heterogeneous, a pattern of change initiated by a major continental migration event at the Early/Middle Miocene boundary, and then reinforced by a global cooling event at c. 14 Ma, and (3) after c. 11 Ma, the climate induces a strong latitudinal differentiation of the faunas, yielding to a significant decrease in the interregional connectivity. The extant endemic situation for small mammals (e.g. Baquero & Tellería, 2001) thus does not appear to be the single and straightforward consequence of the Quaternary glacial cycles, but is shown to have deep historical roots corresponding to global tectonic and mostly climatic events acting as primary drivers of long-term changes.

Since the rapid growth of macroecology in the 1990s, many studies have suggested a control of biodiversity at broad spatial and temporal scale partly independent of the known processes acting on populations at the local scale level (e.g. Hillebrand & Blenckner, 2002; Arita & Rodriguez, 2004). At a regional scale, the metacommunity level proves to be relevant for the description of broad-scale patterns of species diversity and emphasizes the respective role of geographical, climatic and historical (mainly origination/extinction and migration) parameters in structuring and maintaining the diversity of regional pools. Indeed, when compared with climatic fluctuations starting at c. 18 Ma onwards, the biogeographical evolutionary trend described in this paper is coherent and meaningful, illustrating a parallel evolution of interregional faunal affinities and climatic global changes. The correlation of biogeographical events with climatic changes emphasizes the role of the climatic context over the geographical one in generating heterogeneous biogeographical patterns at the continental scale.

The consistency of the inferred evolutionary trend also confirms that the time resolution of this study (biochronological units ranging in a time-scale of 10^5 – 10^6 years) is suitable for

describing long-term changes over several million years in meta-communities. Subsequently, the morphological changes observed within the phyletic lineages (anagenetic evolution) at a time-scale of 10^5 years (e.g. Aguilar & Michaux, 1987; Escarguel *et al.*, 1997) appears faster than the metacommunity evolutionary dynamics. Thus, our results support the hypothesis of a two-level hierarchy of faunal reaction to environmental variations: under moderate environmental variations as observed during the Late Oligocene and Early Miocene, faunal reaction would mainly consist of local extinction and (re-)colonization events as well as phyletic (anagenetic) evolution, whereas more drastic environmental changes as observed from the Middle Miocene onwards would also imply larger faunal reorganization at the inter-metacommunity level.

This hypothesis remains to be further tested from both empirical and theoretical points of view, e.g. carefully investigating the tempo and mode of the variation of evolutionary (speciation and extinction) rates through time, and performing simulation analyses by associating intra- and interregional constraints at a continental and phylogenetic time-scale resolution. In turn, the faunal reaction norms estimated from such deep-time studies could be applied to extant regional metacommunities in order to more realistically model their evolutionary dynamics when faced with global changes.

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

The following supplementary material is available for this article:

Appendix S1 Result matrices for each biochronological unit (the full list of the 626 analysed fossil localities and the 18 successive biogeographical incidence matrices are available on request from the corresponding author)